

Tangential Acceleration of a Five-Bar Linkage in a Collinear Singular Position: Analytical Limiting Formulas

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Abstract

This paper derives analytical limiting formulas for determining the velocity and tangential acceleration of one joint point of a planar five-bar linkage in a collinear singular position. The mechanism is assumed to pass through the singular position along a prescribed continuous branch of motion; therefore, the required kinematic quantities are defined as limiting values from neighbouring nonsingular positions.

The five-bar linkage is decomposed into two coupled four-bar submechanisms, but with moving effective bases. Therefore, the limiting formulas for a four-bar linkage with a fixed base cannot be applied by simple substitution of the submechanism link lengths. The proposed procedure determines the limiting behaviour of both moving-base submechanisms separately and then sums the corresponding partial velocities and partial tangential accelerations at the joint point. After introducing the limiting formulas for the singular position, compact computational formulas for the total velocity and tangential acceleration are also obtained.

The numerical example shows that direct summation of formulas for four-bar linkages with fixed bases gives an incorrect velocity, whereas the velocity obtained by the moving-base procedure is independently confirmed on the basis of the equality of normal accelerations in the collinear position. Additional checks using a near-singular position and a reduction to a four-bar linkage with a fixed base confirm the consistency of the derived formulas.

Keywords: five-bar linkage; collinear singular position; tangential acceleration; limiting kinematic analysis; moving effective base; four-bar submechanism

1. Introduction

Singular positions are among the fundamental difficulties in the kinematic analysis of closed planar mechanisms. This difficulty is especially pronounced in the analysis of tangential acceleration.

Classical literature on the theory of mechanisms contains general relations and various procedures for the kinematic analysis of planar mechanisms [1]–[5]. In more recent literature, singular configurations of closed kinematic chains are most often considered by means of the Jacobian matrix and numerical procedures [6]. Singular configurations of closed kinematic chains have also been analysed by matrix-based procedures [7] and within a general geometric framework [8]. However, the authors are not aware of a closed analytical procedure for determining the tangential acceleration of a joint of a five-bar linkage in a collinear singular position.

For a planar four-bar linkage with a fixed base, closed limiting formulas for the velocity and tangential acceleration of the coupler point have been derived previously [9]. These formulas, however, cannot be applied directly to extracted submechanisms of the five-bar linkage, because their effective bases are not fixed.

Therefore, this paper considers a five-bar linkage in a collinear singular position, with the aim of deriving analytical limiting formulas for velocity and tangential acceleration. The analysis assumes that the mechanism enters the singular position and leaves it along the same continuous branch of motion.

2. Singular four-bar linkage as a reference case

The limiting formulas for a four-bar linkage with a fixed base are used in this paper as a reference case. For completeness, the necessary formulas for velocity and tangential acceleration are given here.

Consider the planar four-bar linkage $B-C-D-E-B$ with fixed base BE , Fig. 1. In the collinear singular position, the coupler point C lies on the same straight line as the remaining joints of the mechanism. If the mechanism passes through this position along a prescribed branch of motion, the velocity of point C can be written in limiting form

Figure 1. Reference four-bar linkage with fixed base BE . Limiting formulas (1) and (2) are obtained for the corresponding collinear position.

$$V_C = V_D \frac{BC}{BE + ED} \left(1 + \sqrt{\frac{BE \cdot CD}{BC \cdot ED}} \right) \quad (1)$$

The corresponding tangential acceleration is

$$a_{CT} = a_{DT} \frac{BC}{BE + ED} \left(1 + \sqrt{\frac{BE \cdot CD}{BC \cdot ED}} \right) \quad (2)$$

3. Five-bar linkage and problem statement

Consider the planar five-bar linkage $A-B-C-D-E-A$, with fixed link EA and with two actuated links, AB and ED , Fig. 2. Point C is the joint point whose velocity and tangential acceleration are to be determined. The analysis concerns the collinear singular position in which all five joints lie on the same straight line.

Figure 2. Planar five-bar linkage $A-B-C-D-E-A$ near the collinear singular position. The fixed link is EA , and the actuated links are AB and ED .

In this position, the instantaneous geometry alone does not determine the motion of the mechanism uniquely. Therefore, the paper does not consider all possible instantaneous motions compatible with the singular geometry. Instead, it is assumed that the mechanism enters the singular position and leaves it along the same continuous branch of motion, without switching to another admissible branch. This removes the instantaneous indeterminacy and allows the required kinematic quantities to be defined as limiting values of the corresponding quantities in neighbouring nonsingular positions.

Before applying the limiting formulas, a sign convention must be adopted. In the following derivation, the positive directions of the angular velocities and angular accelerations of the actuated links are determined according to the adopted convention for the angles. The same convention is also used for the auxiliary angles introduced in the two four-bar submechanisms. In the derivation, the sign of each root is selected according to the direction of change of the corresponding auxiliary angle as the mechanism approaches the singular position.

The five-bar linkage is represented by two coupled four-bar submechanisms. The first submechanism, $E-B-C-D$, is used to determine the partial effect of the motion of link ED on point C . The second submechanism, $D-A-B-C$, is used to determine the partial effect of the motion of link AB on point C . In neither of these two cases is the extracted submechanism a four-bar linkage with a fixed base. Its effective base is a diagonal of the original five-bar linkage and changes during the approach to the singular position. Therefore, the expressions for a four-bar linkage with a fixed base must be replaced by limiting formulas for submechanisms with a moving base.

4. Limiting formulas with a moving base

The two moving-base submechanisms used in the derivation are shown in Fig. 3. For each submechanism, the required quantities are obtained from the limiting derivatives of the moving diagonal and from the angular velocities of the auxiliary angles that tend to zero in the collinear singular position. The signs of the angular velocities and accelerations follow from the adopted convention for the angular coordinates.

Figure 3. Decomposition of the five-bar linkage into moving-base submechanisms near the collinear singular position. Top: first submechanism $E-B-C-D$ with moving effective base EB . Bottom: second submechanism $D-A-B-C$ with moving effective base AD .

4.1. First submechanism E-B-C-D

In the first submechanism, the moving base is the diagonal EB . Its limiting derivatives are determined from the triangle EAB , because the motion of point B is determined by the actuated link AB . In the collinear singular position,

$$\dot{E}B = -\frac{EA \cdot AB}{EB} \omega_{AB}^2, \quad \ddot{E}B = -3 \frac{EA \cdot AB}{EB} \omega_{AB} \varepsilon_{AB}, \quad (3)$$

$$\omega_{EB} = -\frac{AB}{EB} \omega_{AB}, \quad \varepsilon_{EB} = -\frac{AB}{EB} \varepsilon_{AB} \quad (4)$$

The next moving length in the first submechanism is the diagonal DB . Its limiting derivatives follow from the triangle $E-D-B$:

$$\dot{D}B^{(I)} = \dot{E}B - \frac{ED \cdot EB}{DB} (\omega_{ED} - \omega_{EB})^2, \quad (5)$$

$$\ddot{D}B^{(I)} = \ddot{E}B - 3 \frac{ED \cdot EB}{DB} (\omega_{ED} - \omega_{EB})(\varepsilon_{ED} - \varepsilon_{EB}) \quad (6)$$

The limiting angular velocities and angular accelerations of the first pair of auxiliary angles are

$$\dot{\theta}_{1I} = -\frac{ED}{DB} (\omega_{ED} - \omega_{EB}), \quad \ddot{\theta}_{1I} = -\frac{ED}{DB} (\varepsilon_{ED} - \varepsilon_{EB}), \quad (7)$$

$$\dot{\psi}_{1I} = \frac{EB}{ED} \dot{\theta}_{1I}, \quad \ddot{\psi}_{1I} = \frac{EB}{ED} \ddot{\theta}_{1I} \quad (8)$$

The second pair of auxiliary angles is obtained from the limiting behaviour of the triangle $D-B-C$. Since the angle θ_{2I} decreases along the selected branch of motion, the negative branch of the square root is taken:

$$\dot{\theta}_{2I} = -\sqrt{-\frac{\dot{D}B^{(I)} \cdot DC}{DB \cdot BC}}, \quad \ddot{\theta}_{2I} = \frac{\ddot{D}B^{(I)}}{3\dot{D}B^{(I)}} \dot{\theta}_{2I}, \quad (9)$$

$$\dot{\psi}_{2I} = \frac{BC}{DC} \dot{\theta}_{2I}, \quad \ddot{\psi}_{2I} = \frac{BC}{DC} \ddot{\theta}_{2I} \quad (10)$$

For a nonsingular position of the extracted submechanism $E-B-C-D$, the partial velocity of point C can be written in the form

$$V_{C,I}^{ns} = \frac{V_D \cos \psi_{1I} BC}{EB \cos \theta_{1I} + ED \cos \psi_{1I}} \left[1 + \frac{EB \sin(\theta_{1I} + \psi_{1I}) \cos \psi_{2I}}{BC \sin(\theta_{2I} + \psi_{2I}) \cos \psi_{1I}} \right] \quad (11)$$

Here the superscript “ns” denotes the nonsingular formula used before the collinear limit is introduced. Taking formula (11) to the collinear limit gives

$$V_{C,I} = V_D \frac{BC}{DB} \left(1 + \frac{EB}{BC} \frac{\dot{\theta}_{1I} + \dot{\psi}_{1I}}{\dot{\theta}_{2I} + \dot{\psi}_{2I}} \right) \quad (12)$$

The partial tangential acceleration is obtained by differentiating the nonsingular formula (11). The collinear limiting conditions are introduced only after this differentiation. This gives

$$a_{CT,I} = a_{DT} \frac{BC}{DB} \left(1 + \frac{EB}{BC} \frac{\dot{\theta}_{1I} + \dot{\psi}_{1I}}{\dot{\theta}_{2I} + \dot{\psi}_{2I}} \right) + \quad (13)$$

$$+ V_D \frac{EB}{DB} \frac{(\ddot{\theta}_{1I} + \ddot{\psi}_{1I})(\dot{\theta}_{2I} + \dot{\psi}_{2I}) - (\dot{\theta}_{1I} + \dot{\psi}_{1I})(\ddot{\theta}_{2I} + \ddot{\psi}_{2I})}{2(\dot{\theta}_{2I} + \dot{\psi}_{2I})^2}$$

The second term in formula (13) appears because the effective base EB changes during the limiting procedure.

4.2. Second submechanism D-A-B-C

The second submechanism is treated in the same way. Its moving base is the diagonal AD , whose limiting derivatives are determined from the triangle EAD , because the motion of point D is determined by the actuated link ED .

$$\ddot{A}D = -\frac{EA \cdot ED}{AD} \omega_{ED}^2, \quad \ddot{A}D = -3 \frac{EA \cdot ED}{AD} \omega_{ED} \varepsilon_{ED}, \quad (14)$$

$$\omega_{AD} = -\frac{ED}{AD} \omega_{ED}, \quad \varepsilon_{AD} = -\frac{ED}{AD} \varepsilon_{ED} \quad (15)$$

The diagonal DB is then determined from the triangle $A-D-B$, which gives

$$\ddot{D}B^{(II)} = \ddot{A}D - \frac{AB \cdot AD}{DB} (\omega_{AB} - \omega_{AD})^2, \quad (16)$$

$$\ddot{D}B^{(II)} = \ddot{A}D - 3 \frac{AB \cdot AD}{DB} (\omega_{AB} - \omega_{AD})(\varepsilon_{AB} - \varepsilon_{AD}) \quad (17)$$

The limiting angular velocities and angular accelerations of the first pair of auxiliary angles in the second submechanism are

$$\dot{\theta}_{1II} = -\frac{AB}{DB} (\omega_{AB} - \omega_{AD}), \quad \ddot{\theta}_{1II} = -\frac{AB}{DB} (\varepsilon_{AB} - \varepsilon_{AD}), \quad (18)$$

$$\dot{\psi}_{1II} = \frac{AD}{AB} \dot{\theta}_{1II}, \quad \ddot{\psi}_{1II} = \frac{AD}{AB} \ddot{\theta}_{1II} \quad (19)$$

The second pair of auxiliary angles is obtained from the limiting behaviour of the triangle $D-B-C$. Along the selected branch of motion, the negative branch of the square root is again taken:

$$\dot{\theta}_{2II} = -\sqrt{-\frac{\ddot{D}B^{(II)} \cdot BC}{DB \cdot DC}}, \quad \ddot{\theta}_{2II} = \frac{\ddot{D}B^{(II)}}{3\dot{D}B^{(II)}} \dot{\theta}_{2II}, \quad (20)$$

$$\dot{\psi}_{2II} = \frac{DC}{BC} \dot{\theta}_{2II}, \quad \ddot{\psi}_{2II} = \frac{DC}{BC} \ddot{\theta}_{2II} \quad (21)$$

For a nonsingular position of the extracted submechanism $D-A-B-C$, the corresponding partial velocity can be written in the form

$$V_{C,II}^{ns} = \frac{V_B \cos \psi_{1II} DC}{AD \cos \theta_{1II} + AB \cos \psi_{1II}} \left[1 + \frac{AD \sin(\theta_{1II} + \psi_{1II}) \cos \psi_{2II}}{DC \sin(\theta_{2II} + \psi_{2II}) \cos \psi_{1II}} \right] \quad (22)$$

Taking formula (22) to the collinear limit gives

$$V_{C,II} = V_B \frac{DC}{DB} \left(1 + \frac{AD \dot{\theta}_{1II} + \dot{\psi}_{1II}}{DC \dot{\theta}_{2II} + \dot{\psi}_{2II}} \right), \quad (23)$$

Similarly, the partial tangential acceleration associated with the second submechanism is obtained by differentiating the nonsingular formula (22):

$$a_{CT,II} = a_{BT} \frac{DC}{DB} \left(1 + \frac{AD \dot{\theta}_{1II} + \dot{\psi}_{1II}}{DC \dot{\theta}_{2II} + \dot{\psi}_{2II}} \right) + V_B \frac{AD}{DB} \frac{(\ddot{\theta}_{1II} + \ddot{\psi}_{1II})(\dot{\theta}_{2II} + \dot{\psi}_{2II}) - (\dot{\theta}_{1II} + \dot{\psi}_{1II})(\ddot{\theta}_{2II} + \ddot{\psi}_{2II})}{2(\dot{\theta}_{2II} + \dot{\psi}_{2II})^2} \quad (24)$$

The second term in formula (24) has the same origin as the second term in formula (13): it appears because of the limiting change of the effective base AD .

4.3. Superposition at point C

After the two moving-base submechanisms have been treated separately, the velocity and tangential acceleration of point C are obtained by summing the corresponding partial limiting quantities:

$$V_C = V_{C,I} + V_{C,II} \quad (25)$$

$$a_{CT} = a_{CT,I} + a_{CT,II} \quad (26)$$

After substituting the limiting formulas for the singular position for the auxiliary angles into the expressions for the two partial velocities, the total velocity of point C can also be written in compact form

$$V_C = \frac{V_D BC + V_B DC + \sqrt{BC \cdot DC \cdot Q}}{DB} \quad (27)$$

$$Q = \frac{AD}{AB} V_B^2 + \frac{EB}{ED} V_D^2 + 2V_B V_D \quad (28)$$

Here, $V_B = AB \cdot \omega_{AB}$ and $V_D = ED \cdot \omega_{ED}$. In the singular position, $EB = EA + AB$, $AD = EA + ED$ and $DB = BC + DC$.

In the same way, after substituting the limiting formulas for the singular position for the accelerations, the total tangential acceleration can be reduced to the compact computational formula

$$a_{CT} = \frac{a_{DT} \cdot BC + a_{BT} \cdot DC + \sqrt{\frac{BC \cdot DC}{Q}} H}{DB} \quad (29)$$

$$H = \frac{AD}{AB} V_B \cdot a_{BT} + \frac{EB}{ED} V_D \cdot a_{DT} + V_D \cdot a_{BT} + V_B \cdot a_{DT} \quad (30)$$

Here, $a_{BT} = AB \cdot \varepsilon_{AB}$ and $a_{DT} = ED \cdot \varepsilon_{ED}$.

The compact forms also provide a useful check of the limiting procedure. If the motion of point B is stopped, i.e. if $V_B = 0$ and $a_{BT} = 0$, the expression for velocity reduces to the corresponding formula for a four-bar linkage in the dead position, for the submechanism $E-B-C-D$:

$$V_C = V_D \frac{BC}{DB} \left(1 + \sqrt{\frac{EB \cdot DC}{BC \cdot ED}} \right) \quad (31)$$

$$a_{CT} = a_{DT} \frac{BC}{DB} \left(1 + \sqrt{\frac{EB \cdot DC}{BC \cdot ED}} \right) \quad (32)$$

In the notation for the four-bar linkage with a fixed base from Section 2, $DB = BE + ED$ and $DC = CD$. Therefore, for the same configuration branch, formulas (31) and (32) coincide with the formulas for a four-bar linkage with a fixed base.

The superposition used here is not the superposition of two independent physical mechanisms. It represents a decomposition of the limiting response of point C with respect to two prescribed input motions. Therefore, the limiting formulas must first be derived for each moving-base submechanism and only then can the corresponding partial quantities be summed. Direct summation of formulas for four-bar linkages with fixed bases is not correct, because it neglects the change of the effective bases EB and AD .

5. Numerical example and validation

The derived formulas are now applied to the five-bar linkage shown in Fig. 2. The link lengths of the five-bar linkage are $AB = 30$ cm, $BC = 70$ cm, $CD = 50$ cm, $ED = 10$ cm and $EA = 80$ cm.

The numerical example is defined by the initial kinematic data given in Table 1. These values determine the branch of motion leading to the collinear singular position.

Table 1. Initial kinematic data determining the branch of motion of the numerical example

Quantity	Initial value
$\varphi_{ED,0}$	1/3 rad
$\varphi_{AB,0}$	1/3 rad
$\omega_{ED,0}$	1/6 s ⁻¹
$\omega_{AB,0}$	0
ε_{ED}	1/3 s ⁻²
ε_{AB}	2/3 s ⁻²

If time is measured from the initial position, the prescribed motion reaches the collinear singular position at $t = 1$ s. The corresponding input kinematic quantities, which are used in the singular limiting formulas, are determined at that instant and are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Input kinematic quantities in the collinear singular position.

Quantity	Value in the singular position
ω_{AB}	2/3 s ⁻¹
ω_{ED}	0.5 s ⁻¹
ε_{AB}	2/3 s ⁻²
ε_{ED}	1/3 s ⁻²

If the formulas for a four-bar linkage with a fixed base, (1) and (2), are applied directly to the two extracted submechanisms and the obtained results are then summed, the velocity $V_C = 36.5038$ cm/s is obtained.

By applying the moving-base limiting formulas derived in Section 4, the partial velocities obtained from formulas (12) and (23) are $V_{C,I} = 7.4339$ cm/s and $V_{C,II} = 23.9932$ cm/s. According to formula (25), this gives

$$V_C = V_{C,I} + V_{C,II} = 31.4271 \text{ cm/s.}$$

The velocity obtained by the moving-base procedure can be checked independently by means of the equality of normal accelerations in the collinear position, which can be written as

$$-a_{BN} + \frac{(V_C - V_B)^2}{BC} = a_{DN} - \frac{(V_C - V_D)^2}{DC} \quad (33)$$

where $a_{BN} = AB \cdot \omega_{AB}^2$ and $a_{DN} = ED \cdot \omega_{ED}^2$. Substitution of the numerical data gives two mathematical roots. The root corresponding to the considered branch of motion is

$$V_C = 31.4271 \text{ cm/s.}$$

This value confirms the velocity obtained by the limiting moving-base procedure. The difference between this value and the value obtained by direct summation of formulas for a fixed base shows that the formula for a four-bar linkage with a fixed base cannot be applied to extracted submechanisms unless the motion of their effective bases is taken into account.

The corresponding partial tangential accelerations, obtained from formulas (13) and (24), are

$a_{CT,I} = 4.5724 \text{ cm/s}^2$ and $a_{CT,II} = 24.3768 \text{ cm/s}^2$. Therefore, according to formula (26),

$$a_{CT} = a_{CT,I} + a_{CT,II} = 28.9492 \text{ cm/s}^2.$$

The same values are also obtained by direct substitution of the data from Table 2 into the compact computational formulas (27) and (29).

As an additional check, the mechanism was analysed in a near-singular position, at $t = 0.99 \text{ s}$, immediately before the singular instant $t = 1 \text{ s}$. A graphical construction in AutoCAD gave $V_C = 31.1374 \text{ cm/s}$ and $a_{CT} = 29.0417 \text{ cm/s}^2$, while an independent computation in GIM gave $V_C = 31.1369 \text{ cm/s}$ and $a_{CT} = 28.8966 \text{ cm/s}^2$. These values are in good agreement with the limiting analytical values, with the remaining difference arising from the fact that the comparison is made in a near-singular, rather than exactly singular, position.

The results obtained by the different procedures are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison of velocity and tangential acceleration results.

Method	V_C (cm/s)	a_{CT} (cm/s ²)
Direct summation of formulas for a fixed base	36.5038	--
Moving-base limiting procedure	31.4271	28.9492
Near-singular position, AutoCAD, $t = 0.99 \text{ s}$	31.1374	29.0417
Near-singular position, GIM, $t = 0.99 \text{ s}$	31.1369	28.8966

A further check is obtained by reducing the five-bar linkage to a four-bar linkage. If $AB = 0$, with BC adjusted to 40 cm so that the reduced mechanism can reach the collinear singular position, and if therefore $\omega_{AB} = 0$ and $\varepsilon_{AB} = 0$, the moving-base formulas reduce to the case of a four-bar linkage with a fixed base. For the corresponding numerical data, the procedure derived here gives $V_C = 9.25 \text{ cm/s}$ and $a_{CT} = 6.17 \text{ cm/s}^2$, which are the same values as those obtained from the formulas for a four-bar linkage with a fixed base from Section 2.

6. Discussion

The numerical example shows that the failure of direct superposition of formulas for a four-bar linkage with a fixed base is not caused by superposition itself, but by the application of those formulas outside their range of validity. In the five-bar linkage, the extracted submechanisms have effective bases that change during the approach to the singular position.

The proposed procedure avoids this difficulty by not treating the singular position as an isolated static geometry. Instead, the singular position is approached through neighbouring nonsingular positions along the selected branch of motion. The derivatives of the moving bases and the angular velocities of the auxiliary angles carry information about this approach.

The derived formulas are valid for the prescribed branch of motion along which the mechanism passes through the collinear singular position. They give the limiting velocity and tangential acceleration for the prescribed passage through that position. A different choice of branch or a change of the direction of motion in the singular position would require a corresponding change in the signs of the auxiliary angular velocities and accelerations. Therefore, the sign convention and the selected branch of motion must be specified before the formulas are applied.

7. Conclusion

This paper has derived analytical limiting formulas for the velocity and tangential acceleration of one joint point of a planar five-bar linkage in a collinear singular position. The mechanism was decomposed

into two four-bar submechanisms with moving effective bases, and the limiting formulas were derived separately for each of them.

It has been shown that the formulas for a four-bar linkage with a fixed base cannot be applied directly to extracted submechanisms of the five-bar linkage, because their effective bases change during the approach to the singular position.

The obtained partial velocities and partial tangential accelerations are summed at the considered joint point. The numerical example, the check based on the equality of normal accelerations, the near-singular position and the reduction to a four-bar linkage confirm the consistency of the derived formulas.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank the developers of the GIM software for providing access to the program used for the independent kinematic check in a near-singular position.

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